

and TKM6 — were resistant to the disease under artificial inoculation.

Chemical control trials for 2 consecutive seasons showed that 3 sprays of carbenazim (0.05%), benomyl (0.05%), and Brestanol (0.1%) gave good disease control in the field. ■

Epidemiological adaptation by the rice blast pathogen during adverse weather

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During kharif 1979, dark-brown to blackish lesions were observed on the panicle-bearing and ensheathed lower internodes and nodes of the stems in plants of a susceptible local rice cultivar Tulsiphool at the Faizabad RRS. The lesions were either eye-shaped or irregular; the latter were more common on the panicle axis and below its base. Blurred brown blotches appeared on the sheath encasing the affected part of the stem. There was mycelial growth with abundant sporulation on the ensheathed lesions on nodes and internodes (see photo). The naked lesions rarely sporulated. In advanced stages the lesions on the sheath also sporulated underneath.

Ensheathed lesions on nodes and internodes, and blotches on the sheath encasing the affected part of the stem of the cultivar Tulsiphool. Faizabad, U.P., India.

No breaking at the panicle base was seen.

Long sheaths encasing the nodes and internodes are a peculiar characteristic of Tulsiphool and appear to provide favorable conditions for the development of those symptoms. The disease appeared during the last 2 weeks of October when night temperatures were relatively mild and considerable dew collected on the leaves. The microclimate was therefore suitable for disease development in the ensheathed nodes and

internodes. The general weather during the growing season, however, was unusually dry and not favorable for blast development (see table).

The occurrence of the disease on highly susceptible cultivars such as Tulsiphool under adverse situations appears epidemiologically significant. However, the disease may only be regarded as a "sleeper disease" in Eastern U. P. because of the requirement of critical weather parameters for its development. ■

Monthly meteorological data, June to November 1979, at the Faizabad Rice Research Station, India.

Weather parameter	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov
Rainfall (mm)	27.2	182.2	31.2	21.2	39.0	22.4
Rainy days (no.)	2	12	4	2	4	1
Relative humidity (%)	63	84	81	79	85	84
Max temp (° C)	38.7	33.7	34.6	35.7	33.5	32.0
Bright sunshine (h)	9.7	6.9	9.7	9.5	9.4	8.9

Incidence and chemical control of ufra in boro fields

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A survey of ufra disease on boro rice was conducted in the Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra Project area in 1979 because ufra had appeared on transplanted aman rice in that area in 1978. Skipping 1979, the disease reappeared in 1980 and affected about 1.2 ha of transplanted IR8 severely in boro (Nov to Apr). Eighty percent of the crop of the heavily infected patches was completely lost.

To reduce disease severity and yield

loss due to ufra, carbofuran 3G was soil incorporated in the mild ufra-infected portion. Reduction in disease spread and severity was observed in the treated plots compared with the control (see table).

The yields of the treated plots and the control differed significantly. Carbofuran 3G at 34 kg/ha appeared best in controlling ufra and reducing yield loss. ■

Yield and ufra severity in carbofuran-treated and control plots of IR8, Dacca, Bangladesh. 1980:

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Ufra severity (%)
Control	1.43 b	5.67 b
17 kg carbofuran 3G/ha	1.69 b	4.67 ab
34 kg carbofuran 3G/ha	2.93 a	1.67 a

^a Mean of 3 replications. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of time of nitrogen application on weed growth and yield of dry-seeded rice

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Different amounts of nitrogen were incorporated into the soil before planting and applied as topdressing to dry-seeded wetland IR36 rice to determine the effect of time of nitrogen application on weed growth and crop yield.

Some plots received no basal applica-